

Spatial Autoregression as a Means of Measuring Neighbourhood Effect in Latvian Parliamentary Elections

Lidia Zhirnova¹

Abstract

Neighbourhood effect as an independent voting factor was conceptualized back in late 1960-s in the works by D.R. Reynolds and K.R. Cox and was proved on a local level a decade later by R. Huckfeldt and J. Sprague. Nowadays it is possible to measure the neighbourhood effect nationwide by the means of spatial statistical analysis, using the spatial autoregressive model that adds a spatial lag to the list of independent variables. This approach was employed by I. Okunev to prove the significance of the neighbourhood effect at the 2016 US presidential elections. The current article used the same instrument to evaluate the neighbourhood effect at the Latvian Saeima elections in 2010-2022. Although the Latvian political and electoral system is still mainly defined by the ethnolinguistic cleavage, the neighbourhood effect was identified for both “Russian” and “Latvian” parties. It was the largest for the Progressive party in 2022, the Development/For! alliance in 2018 and the Greens and Farmers Union in 2011.

Key Words:

electoral geography, spatial analysis, voting behaviour, Saeima, spatial lag

¹ research fellow, Center for Spatial Analysis in International Relations, Institute for International Studies, MGIMO-University

Introduction

Although ethnolinguistic cleavage remains the main factor of electoral behavior in Latvia, the country's political system is currently transforming due to the fragmentation of the Russian-speaking electoral field. At the 2022 Saeima elections the Harmony party, a long-standing monopolist of the Russian-speaking votes with a largest Saeima faction, failed to cope with acute competition and did not pass to the parliament. As a result, a large Russian-speaking community is currently represented in the Saeima by a relatively small faction of a new For Stability! party that is even less capable to influence government policies.

These circumstances increase the importance of analyzing other voting factors, whose significance may later increase. These include the neighborhood effect, i.e., the support for a party in a certain region being influenced by the support in the neighboring regions. The article studies the neighborhood effect at the Latvian parliamentary elections in the years 2010-2022.

The research aims at measuring the significance of the neighborhood effect in the electoral support for Latvian parties at the Saeima elections over the studied period. In order to do that, the results of the classical regression model of the voting for parliamentary parties broken down by municipalities are compared with the autoregressive model that takes into account the spatial lag, i.e. the support for the party in the neighboring regions. If accounting for spatial lag increases the explanatory power of the model, it attests to the existence of the neighborhood effect.

The Electoral System of the Latvian Republic

The Latvian unicameral parliament called the Saeima is elected every four years in five electoral districts (Riga, Kurzeme, Vidzeme, Zemgale and Latgale) with a 5% threshold². The indexes of the effective number of parties attest to the increasing fragmentation of the party system (Golosov 2010, 188). Based on the results of the 2022 election, the Laakso-Taagepera index reached 11,8, meaning that apart from the seven parliamentary factions five more parties have a considerable impact on the party system. The Golosov index amounts to 5,4, which is also quite high. It is lower because it leaves out of the consideration those parties that were strongly lagging behind the winner of the election. At the 2018 election the Laakso-Taagepera index was lower – 8,4 (which is still quite high), so its growth indicates the steep increase in fragmentation, which can be linked to the fragmentation of the Russian-speaking party landscape in 2022. And the Golosov index in 2018 was slightly higher (5,8), which can be, probably, explained by the turmoil around the leader of the election that is central to this index: in 2022 the long-lasting leader of

² Saeimas vēlēšanu likums (22.01.2022 red.) Accessed 06.06.2023. <https://likumi.lv/doc.php?id=35261>.

the election – the Harmony party – could not overcome the 5% threshold, and the overall gap between the new frontrunner and other parties decreased.

The ethnolinguistic cleavage between the Russian-speaking and the Latvian population remains the main characteristic of the Latvian political system and electoral behaviour. The party landscape is still clearly divided into the “Latvian” and the “Russian”, and over the last decade only few political powers managed to attract both Latvian and non-Latvian voters (Zhirnova 2022, 154). In case of the Latvian party system the ethnolinguistic divide in fact replaced a more traditional division into the left and the right. The label of the left or the centre-left parties usually stands not for an alternative socio-economic agenda, but for the “Russian” parties, whereas the “Latvian” parties are usually referred to as right or centre-right (Vorotnikov 2018, 85; Ikstens, Balcere 2019, 258).

Although Russian speakers account for about a third of the Latvian population³, the electorate of the “Russian” parties is considerably limited by the alien (non-citizen) status. After the restoration of independence, the Latvian government refused to grant citizenship to those permanent residents, whose ancestors had not lived in Latvia before 1940, giving them alien passports instead and depriving them of the right to vote at any level. Usually those were the Russian speakers who had moved to Latvia in the Soviet times and their descendants. Although the alien status was initially introduced as a temporary one, nowadays every tenth Latvian is an alien. Consequently, Russian speakers account for only about a quarter of Latvian citizens, considerably less than the overall proportion of the population⁴.

The representatives of the “Russian” parties Harmony and For Stability! occasionally speak in favour of changing the voting system from the proportional to the majority electoral system (examples include the interview of the former Harmony leader J. Jānis Urbanovičs⁵, the electoral programme of For Stability!⁶). However, such a transformation will increase the geographic favouritism of the electoral system, i.e. its inclination towards territorial differentiation, which favours large national and small regional parties (Okunev 2023, 101). In this case the “Russian” parties will be put at a disadvantage and will run the risk of losing even

³ Iedzīvotāju skaits un īpatsvars pēc tautības un valstiskās piederības gada sākumā. Centrālā statistikas pārvalde. Accessed 30.09.2021. <https://stat.gov.lv/lv/statistikas-temas/iedzivotaji/iedzivotaju-skaits/tabulas/ire060-iedzivotaju-skaits-un-ipatsvars-pec>.

⁴ 60,8 % Latvijas iedzīvotāju dzimtā valoda ir latviešu. Centrālā statistikas pārvalde. Accessed 30.09.2021. <https://www.csb.gov.lv/lv/statistika/statistikas-temas/iedzivotaji/meklet-tema/2747-608-latvijas-iedzivotaju-dzimta-valoda-ir-latviesu>.

⁵ Krautmanis M. Jānis Urbanovičs: Varu tautai! Neatkarīgā Rīta Avīze. 24.10.2014. Accessed 06.06.2023. <https://nra.lv/politika/127735-janis-urbanovics-varu-tautai.htm>

⁶ Politiska partija Stabilitātei! Priekšvēlēšanu programma: Latvijas Vestnesis. Accessed 06.06.2023. <https://www.vestnesis.lv/op/2022/175.24>.

the current unimpressive representation, because the Russian speaking voters do not outnumber the Latvians in any of the electoral districts.

Previous Research

The neighbourhood effect in elections, when the support for a party is likely to be higher in the regions surrounded by those regions where the support for the party is high, was conceptualized back in 1969 in the works of D.R. Reynolds (1969) and K.R. Cox (1969). Several decades later its significance was proved on a local level in an experiment by R. Huckfeldt and J. Sprague (1995). However, it was not until lately when the development of computer technologies and geoinformation systems allowed to evaluate the neighbourhood effect on a nationwide level using spatial analysis, namely, spatial autoregression. This instrument was employed by I. Okunev (2023, 267) to prove the independent influence of the neighbourhood effect on the outcome of the 2016 US presidential campaign and provide a quantitative estimate of this effect. In this study I. Okunev's methodology is applied to Latvia.

Such an approach of measuring neighbourhood effect has not yet been applied to Latvian elections, although the Latvian electoral system is regularly studied both in Latvia and abroad. As a rule, researchers focus on the ethnolinguistic cleavage as the main characteristic of Latvia's social and political structure.

For instance, the main territorial cleavages are described in a large chapter devoted to the Latvian electoral system in the book from the Modern Electoral Systems series published under the auspice of the Russian Central Electoral Commission. The authors of the chapter N. Mezhevich and A. Solopenko (2021) state that territorial cleavages of the voting behaviour mainly replicate the uneven settlement of the main two ethnolinguistic groups. The Russian speakers, who rather predictably support the "Russian" parties that appeal to them, mostly live in the capital and other large cities as well as Latgale, a region bordering on Russia and Belarus and enjoying cultural and economic specificity. The votes for the "Russian" parties are dispensed accordingly, concentrating primarily in Riga and Latgale. The urban-rural cleavage between polyethnic cities and primarily Latvian countryside is also in place, with ethnic Latvians in cities and in villages tending to support different parties.

A comparative study of electoral cleavages in Latvia, Lithuania, Estonia, Russia and Ukraine aiming at finding regions of electoral anomalies also indicated that in Latvia such a region is Latgale with a significant non-Latvian population and strong support for "Russian" parties (Meleshevich 2006, p. 119). However, a closer study of Latgalian municipalities (Paiders 2014) could not find any considerable changes in the voting behaviour closer to the Russian or the Belorussian border. The

ethnolinguistic factor and the appeal of specific charismatic candidates proved to be of greater importance.

To sum up, most studies view territorial cleavages of the voting behaviour in Latvia as a reflection of the social structure. This article supplements this approach by considering the spatial structure of the society, i.e., the neighbourhood effect.

Data and Method

The research is based on the official result of the parliamentary elections in Latvia over the five latest electoral cycles (2010, 2011, 2014, 2018 and 2022)⁷. The data is analyzed on a municipal level. From 2009 to 2021 Latvia was administratively divided into 119 municipalities, so the Central Electoral Commission provided the voting data for this division. The results of the 2022 elections were published according to the new administrative division with 43 municipalities.

Apart from the parliamentary parties the results of the Latvian Russian Union were included in the study. Despite the fact that it did not manage to get to Saeima over the studied period, it retained its importance for the Russian-speaking community and both the municipal and European parliamentary representation.

Ethnolinguistic statistics are taken from the 2011 census⁸, because it was the last time, when the Central Statistical Bureau of Latvia provided the data on the proportion of the Russian-speaking citizens in municipalities. Only the proportion of Russian residents in regions is available for the later period, however, it appears unsuitable for the needs of the research, because it includes aliens who have no right to vote. Besides for Latvia the cleavage between Latvians and Russian-speakers is more relevant than that with ethnic Russians (Simonyan 2022, 145). Ethnicity is a relatively stable characteristic, so the 2011 data can be used with certain caution. Of course, all ethnolinguistic statistics are relative rather than precise, but they can help to shape the understanding of the key characteristics of the studied population.

To check the hypothesis about the importance of the neighbourhood effect for the electoral behaviour in Latvia, the spatial autoregressive model (SAR) is employed, adding the spatial lag, i.e. the average value of the dependent variable in the neighbouring regions. If adding the spatial lag increases the explanatory power of the regression model (R-squared), it allows to suggest that the neighbourhood effect

⁷ Saeimas vēlēšanas. Centrālā vēlēšanu komisija. Accessed 08.06.2023. <https://www.cvk.lv/lv/saeimas-velesanas>.

⁸ Latvijas 2011. gada tautas skaitīšanas rezultāti. Centrālā statistikas pārvalde. Accessed 03.03.2021 <https://stat.gov.lv/lv/statistikas-temas/iedzivotaji/iedzivotaju-skaitis/publikacijas-un-infografikas/1299-latvijas-2011>.

is a significant variable with an independent influence on the election outcome (Okunev 2023a, 258).

The dependent variable in the study is the voting results of parliamentary parties in the five latest electoral cycles. The main independent variable is the percentage of the Russian-speaking citizens in the municipalities. Both regression models – the classical (CL) and the spatial lag (SAR) – were computed using the GeoDa software (the detailed manual can be found here: Okunev 2023b, 220-226). The results are represented in Table 1. Three parameters are shown for each calculation: the R-squared, the Akaike information criterion and the logarithmic likelihood. The two latter figures allow to compare the quality of the classical and the spatial regression models: the higher logarithmic likelihood and lower Akaike criterion indicate higher quality of a model (Okunev 2023a, 261). The final table includes only those results, when the p-value of F-statistics, accounting for the overall quality of the model, the p-value the Lagrange multiplier, indicating whether the spatial autoregression can be used, as well as the p-value each of each variable less than 0,05, which is an acceptable significance level for social sciences.

The Results of the Regression Analysis

As the Table 1 shows, in all cases with an acceptable statistical mistake, accounting for the spatial lag, i.e. the support for the party in the neighbouring municipalities, increased the explanatory power of the regression model, indicating the neighbourhood effect. Moreover, the autoregressive models were of higher quality as they had higher log-likelihood and lower Akaike criterion.

The strongest neighbourhood effect was found in the support of the centre-left Progressive party in 2022, the year of its debut at the Saeima elections, when it got 6,16% and 10 parliamentary seats. The results of the party weakly correlate with the number of Russian-speaking citizens in the region (R-squared 0,156), such a regression model cannot be used for analysis. However, adding the spatial lag increases the explanatory power by 0,36 to 0,539, which shows weak dependence, but makes the model suitable for use.

Table 1.

Classical (CL) and spatial lag (SAR) regression models of the Saeima election results in 2010-2022 (empty cell: a high p-value, crossed cell: the party did not participate in the election).

Parties		2010		2011		2014		2018		2022	
		CL	SAR	CL	SAR	CL	SAR	CL	SAR	CL	SAR
Harmony	R-squared	0,919	0,928	0,954	0,958	0,942	0,945	0,951	0,955	0,920	0,938
	Log-lik.	-336	-330	-443	-414	-298	-295	-275	-270	-63	-58
	Akaike	677	667	891	834	600	597	555	547	130	122
Latvian Russian Union	R-squared									0,827	0,843
	Log-lik.									-68	-67
	Akaike									140	139
New Unity	R-squared	0,573	0,718	0,484	0,718	0,152	0,319			0,500	0,720
	Log-lik.	-393	-371	-338	-307	-359	-350			-126	-115
	Akaike	790	750	679	620	723	705			255	236
Greens and Farmers Union	R-squared	0,447	0,601	0,207	0,539	0,360	0,634			0,091	0,345
	Log-lik.	-398	-382	-374	-348	-414	-387			-144	-139
	Akaike	801	771	751	702	832	780			297	284
For a Good Latvia / Latvia First	R-squared	0,151	0,229								
	Log-lik.	-287	-283								
	Akaike	578	571								
National Alliance	R-squared	0,429	0,608	0,494	0,769	0,501	0,784	0,435	0,610		
	Log-lik.	-260	-241	-320	-280	-341	-298	-305	-287		
	Akaike	525	489	644	565	686	601	614	580		

Zatlers' Reform Party	R-squared			0,697	0,714						
	Log-lik.			-327	-324						
	Akaike			658	654						
Development / For!	R-squared							0,275	0,632	0,092	0,268
	Log-lik.							-306	-273	-120	-117
	Akaike							615	552	245	240
Latvian Regional Alliance/ United List	R-squared					0,142	0,180			0,282	0,413
	Log-lik.					-298	-296			-134	-130
	Akaike					560	598			272	268
Conservatives	R-squared							0,503	0,553		
	Log-lik.							-296	-291		
	Akaike							597	589		
KPV LV	R-squared							0,556	0,698		
	Log-lik.							-316	-297		
	Akaike							636	600		
Stability!	R-squared									0,907	0,917
	Log-lik.									-91	-89
	Akaike									186	184
Progressives	R-squared									0,156	0,516
	Log-lik.									-80	-71
	Akaike									164	147

The neighbourhood effect was almost as strong for the alliance Development/For! In 2018 (R-squared increased from 0,275 to 0,632 by 0,357) and for the Greens and Farmers Union in 2011 (R-squared increased from 0,207 to 0,539 by 0,332). In all these cases accounting for spatial lag helped increase the explanatory power of the models higher than 0,5, which made them applicable for analysis.

As for the “Russian” parties (among the studied those are the Harmony, the Latvian Russian Union and the Stability!), the neighbourhood effect also influenced their support, but it usually did not account for more than few per cent of the dispersion. It is probably linked to the fact that the dispersion of votes for them is mostly explained by the regional proportion of the Russian-speaking citizens (R-squared was more than 0,9 for the Harmony and the Stability! and more than 0,8 for the Latvian Russian Union). However, accounting for the spatial lag when analyzing the voting support for the Harmony in 2011 helped to increase the explanatory power of the model from 0,531 to 0,734 by 0,203..

Conclusion

Spatial autoregression allowed to prove the significance of the neighbourhood effect as an independent factor of the voting behaviour in all the studied electoral cycles. The effect was the strongest for the Progressives in 2022, the Development/For! in 2018 and the Greens and Farmers Union in 2011. The neighbourhood effect influenced the electoral support for the “Russian” parties as well, but for them it was not so strong, which can be explained by the paramount importance of the ethnolinguistic factor for these parties. Accounting for the spatial lag allows to ensure a deeper understanding of the voting mechanisms by adding complementing the analysis of the social structure of the electorate by its spatial characteristics.

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